

Social media: What impact on the reputation and e-reputation of SMEs in the Souss Massa region

Les médias sociaux : Quel impact sur la réputation et la e-réputation des PME de la région Souss Massa

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Abstract

This exploratory study is part of the perspective of shedding light on the use of social media by SMEs in the Souss Massa region and the impact of these media on their reputation. To this end, we conducted a study with a limited sample of SMEs in the region through semi-directive interviews with 22 managers of these companies. The results obtained showed that social media have a positive impact on the reputation and notoriety of the companies that were the subject of the research. A number of contributions, limitations and research perspectives are discussed.

Keywords: Digital communication; Social media; reputation; e-reputation; SMEs.

Résumé

Cette étude exploratoire s'inscrit dans la perspective de mettre la lumière sur le recours des PME de la région Souss Massa aux médias sociaux et l'impact de ces médias sur leur réputation et e-réputation. Dans ce but, nous avons réalisé une étude auprès d'un échantillon restreint des PME de la région à travers des entretiens semi directifs avec 22 responsables de ces entreprises. Les résultats obtenus ont montré que les médias sociaux ont un impact positif sur la réputation et la notoriété des entreprises qui ont fait l'objet de recherche. Un certain nombre de contributions, de limites ainsi que de perspectives de recherche sont discutées.

Mots clés : Communication digitale; Médias sociaux; réputation; e-réputation; PME.

Introduction

In all organizations, reputation and digital communication strategy have become inseparable. We often talk about the image of organizations following their presence on social media.

However, in a globalized environment where the economy is constantly evolving, businesses need to expand their presence on social media. A digital communication strategy helps create a unique brand image and improve the reputation and notoriety of companies.

This article therefore aims to test the use of social media by SMEs in the Souss Massa region and the impact of these media on their reputation and e-reputation. Therefore, the main question of the article will be: To what extent does the use of social media contribute to improving the reputation of SMEs in the Souss Massa region?

In order to respond to this problem, we have formulated some proposals, the first of which is that SMEs in the Souss Massa region use social media to be able to control and manage their reputation.

Our second proposition is that the reputation of SMEs is not affected by their interactions on social media.

The third proposition is that the adoption of an effective policy on various social media strongly contributes to improving the reputation of SMEs.

To respond to this problem, we considered using a posture which is mainly inspired by interpretivism following a holistic inductive mode of reasoning. This reasoning consists of discovering and constructing reality. In this sense, the present study is structured around three axes. The first axis refers to the main theoretical foundations underlying social media in relation to corporate reputation. The second axis presents the methodological choices and the area of investigation. The third axis concerns all the results linked to the problem posed and the discussion of these results.

1. Social media and corporate reputation at the crossroads of different theoretical conceptions

In order to fully understand the contribution of social media to improving the reputation and notoriety of companies, literature on the basic concepts used appears necessary.

1.1. Social media as a new form of communication

The term "social media" refers to a set of Web 2.0 technologies that enable the creation, sharing, and enrichment of content produced by users. These Internet tools allow everyone to generate collective intelligence and collaborate on projects.

Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) also point out that the term "social media" refers to " a set of online applications based on the ideology and technique of Web 2.0 and promoting the creation and exchange of user-created content » (p. 61).

Thus Antoine Dupin (2010), specifies that it is "all online platforms allowing the creation of social interactivity between various users around digital content (photos, texts, videos) and this at varying degrees of affinity. They are at the center of all attention, their audience is growing, and they benefit from increased interest from companies or institutions. They also constitute a new shift in the dissemination of information and are in line with the requirements of new marketing and communication technologies.

Lewis (2010) noted that "social media" is simply a "label for digital technologies that people can use to connect, interact, produce, and share content" (p. 2).

Therefore, we say that social media is a site in which three key elements are integrated: technology, social interaction, and content creation.

Howard and Parks (2012) gave a much more complex definition of social media, specifying that it consists of three parts: "(a) the information infrastructure and tools intended to generate and disseminate content; (b) content in the digital form of personalized messages, news, ideas, and cultural products; and (c) the people, organizations, and industries producing and consuming digital content" (p. 362). They go on to say that in the literature, social media is generally characterized not by its attributes and features, but by simply invoking particular programs like Facebook or YouTube. Although a more in-depth definition, this focus on particular instruments can be problematic because it overlooks actual and prospective social impacts and restricts possible contributions to theory building, limiting application to studies descriptive.

While precise, this definition is obviously complex and technical. We, therefore, propose another definition, a somewhat simpler, but perhaps more understandable explanation: social

media are Internet-based communication channels that allow users to engage and present themselves to audiences both broad and limited, which take advantage of user-created content and the perception of contact with others, in real-time or asynchronously.

1.2. The most important social media

Certainly, the world of social media is evolving, the following table presents the most important social media today:

Table No. 1: Types of media

Social networks	<p>Social networks are spaces where “friends” can share information. They are either professional (Viadeo, LinkedIn, etc.) or non-professional (Copains d'avant, Facebook, etc.), but this distinction fades as the possibilities for segmenting "friends" develop (BLOCH, 2012).</p> <p>People can use social media to “write, comment, copy and paste, mix, post, share or exchange photographs, videos, links, and tags on sites featuring themselves and their relational worlds” (Ziegler, 2016).</p>
Media sharing networks	<p>The main objective of these sites is to exchange media, mainly images (Instagram, Photobucket, etc.) and videos (Dailymotion, SlideShare, YouTube, etc.).</p>
Crowdsourcing	<p>Crowdsourcing sites include Wikipedia, 4chan and others, as well as rating sites such as tripadvisor.fr for tourism, testntrust.com and ciao.fr for goods or services. These sites are successful because Internet users contribute to and improve them.</p>
Blogs	<p>Basic web page, mainly used to supplement information (Benabdelhak, 2020).</p> <p>A blog page be corporate (to promote a company and improve its visibility), individual (personal) or collaborative (with many contributors).</p>
Miniblogs	<p>A miniblog is anything that is too short to be published</p>

	<p>on a blog, but too long to be published in a tweet. Photos, video clips, quotes, short blog posts, news, diagrams... Miniblogs are used to communicate thoughts, points of view, links, and funny pictures. Tumblr and Posterous are popular miniblogging sites. (O'BRIEN, 2010).</p>
Microblogging networks	<p>Twitter is the most popular of these microblogging networks. Bookmarking sites such as Delicious and Digg are also included in certain circumstances (O'BRIEN, op.cit.).</p> <p>Its operation prioritizes three key requirements of crisis communication: simplicity, urgency and distribution.</p>
Podcasts (internet radio)	<p>Podcasts are a great way to bring your brand to life and reach your target audience. A successful podcast strategy allows a business (or individual) to communicate directly with its customers and attract new ones.</p>
Merchant sites and consumer review sites	<p>Recommendations are very important on this type of site. It is also the most effective technique for a business to persuade customers to test its goods or services. Examples include eBay, Amazon, Yelp, Etsy, and others.</p>
Event organization sites	<p>They allow you to specify the events in which you wish to participate, whether virtual (webinars) or live (parties, networking evenings, conferences, seminars).</p>

Source : Authors

Thus, social media can be classified according to their use: **Professional social media** like Viadeo, LinkedIn, Xing They are intended for professional networking, but also allow the sharing of links. Content-sharing **social networks** include not only the link and document sharing sites mentioned previously but also video-sharing sites like Youtube and Dailymotion, as well as photo-sharing sites like Instagram, Flickr, or Picasa. **Entertainment social media** like the famous Facebook, the use is mainly intended for the "individual", but also for the

"professional" who can intervene behind the scenes. **Social media for sharing expression**, are the social platforms indicated beforehand, but also forums, blogs, microblogs such as Twitter, wikis, etc.

1.3. The specificities and characteristics of social media

To better understand the concept of social network it is necessary to address its specificities and characteristics. Stenger and Coutant (2013) clearly detailed these specificities “they consider that social media: are based on the idea of mass participation and expression, which encourages Internet users to provide the majority of the content of these sites ; allow any Internet user to participate using simple tools and applications; having almost no cost of participation for Internet users, but which has a price or which can be perceived as a contract involving the tracking, profiling and exploitation of public data; offer constantly evolving content, following a logic of flow, made up of testimonials ("jokey", "serious", "ordinary"...), comments (by reacting to previous content), judgments/assessments (evaluations, notations...) and sharing of files/resources (image, text, sound, video...); constitute the product of the confluence of use, technology, economic strategies and their progressive construction; are the medium for a wide range of social activities and conventions, which requires a better understanding of all social media” (p. 109).

Dewing (2010) outlined the characteristics of social media and noted that it influences the way people engage online, giving rise to new forms of cooperation and conversation. One such characteristic is data durability, which refers to the notion that most materials uploaded to social media platforms are likely to remain there forever. Other characteristics of social media include reproducibility (the ability to copy and distribute content) and searchability (content can be easily found using search engines). Another essential feature is accessibility: one can access social media at any time and from any place where there is an Internet connection.

The dynamics of virtual social interactions are determined by these characteristics. Therefore, the “invisibility” of the reader raises concerns about the context, timing, and intelligibility of a message. Additionally, just as it is difficult to predict who will read social media information, it is not always clear who is posting it and why. Businesses, for example, can use social media to market articles by creating fake blogs or sponsoring posts on social media platforms.

1.4. Business Reputation

Corporate reputation is a key concept in business management that has attracted the attention of many authors over the years.

Fombrun (1996) defines reputation as a perceptual representation of a company's past actions and future prospects that describes the company's overall attractiveness to all its key stakeholders relative to its leading competitors.

Boistel (2014) considers that reputation is the good or bad opinion that different audiences have of a company, based on their experiences, beliefs, emotions, knowledge, and impressions. This overall perception is built from a set of elements communicated by the company and results in a strong reputation when they are perceived in a similar way by different audiences and accepted by employees. In this sense, reputation shapes the opinion of employees, customers, competitors, investors and the public, regarding the identity, actions, statements, and representation of a company (Cailleba, 2009).

Frydman (2008), states that a company's reputation is the result of the integration of its ethical behaviors and financial performance. He considers that reputation can be seen as a source of added value for the company, can attract investments, improve relations with stakeholders and promote customer loyalty.

According to Gotsi and Wilson (2001), a company's reputation is established through the constant evaluation of its stakeholders, who are based on their direct experiences with the company as well as on any other type of communication and symbol providing information on the company's actions or comparing them to those of its main competitors.

Boistel (2016) asserts that the notion of an organization's reputation is more recent and broader than that of corporate image. The latter is in fact dependent on the favorable or unfavorable perception of a particular stakeholder, while reputation takes into account all stakeholders and is considered more stable.

To summarize, we use the diagram created by the Reputation Institute of New York, which illustrates how a company's reputation spreads through all aspects of it.

Figure No. 1: The levers of reputation

Source: (Reputation Institute, 2017)

According to the Reputation Institute, reputation is supported by seven key factors, depicted in this illustration:

- The quality of products and services, the correspondence between expectations and the quality offered, as well as the quality-price ratio;
- The transparency and openness of the company, as well as its business ethics, in terms of governance;
- The company's social and environmental responsibility, as well as its commitment to important causes, in terms of citizenship;
- Fair remuneration of employees and their well-being in the workplace, in terms of employment;
- The capacity for innovation and adaptation of the market, in terms of innovation;
- The charisma and credibility of the leaders, as well as the quality of their management and their vision for the future, in terms of leadership;
- Profitability and growth prospects, in terms of performance.

Ultimately, corporate reputation is a multidimensional concept that is perceived in different ways by authors. Some view reputation as a perceptual representation of a company's past

actions and future prospects that can help describe the company's attractiveness relative to its competitors, while others view reputation as a perception based on the ethical actions and financial performance of the company.

1.5. The transition from reputation to e-reputation of a company

E-reputation is the perception that Internet users have of a company or an organization in general on the Internet. This perception can be influenced by a variety of factors such as online comments, reviews, and social media posts. As Castellano and Dutot (2013) point out, Web 2.0 has allowed consumers to have a significant effect on a company's reputation due to the sharing and social presence characteristics offered by Web 2.0.

For some, online reputation is considered an important aspect of a company's overall reputation, while for others it represents a separate entity that must be managed independently.

E-reputation, according to the definition of Paquerot et al (2011), is the reputation built on the basis of the overall perception that stakeholders will have of an object, based on all the information disseminated on the internet. In this sense Frochot and Molinaro (2008) emphasize that: “e-reputation called cyber reputation, digital reputation or even web reputation is the image that Internet users have of a company or a person based on information circulated about oneself on the Web, what is said by others about oneself, messages disseminated by various Internet users (customers, competitors, employees, etc.) or even traces left involuntarily” (p.13). According to this definition, e-reputation also appears to be close to the image on the internet. In the same sense, Alloing (2013) defines e-reputation as the image that Internet users have of a brand or a person online. In this context, this digital reputation plays a role in building the identity of a brand by differentiating it from its competitors. The e-reputation research observatory Blueboat (2009) further defines e-reputation by analogy with image: “e-reputation is made up of the image that the Internet user has of a company based on all the content that is accessible on the web through different sources blogs, forums, social networks, consumer review sites. It goes through prescribers who give positive or negative opinions. It is important for a company to monitor what is being said in order to intervene if necessary.”

It appears from these definitions that e-reputation is considered a component of reputation, but this is particularly analyzed from the angle of the use of the Internet as a medium.

However, it is also important to note that online reputation appears to have its own specific mechanisms.

2. Methodological choices and area of investigation

In terms of methodology, the design of our study is based on an interpretivist epistemological position. According to Klenke (2008), this approach is based on the idea that social reality is constructed through the processes of interpretation and communication between social actors. Researchers use qualitative methods to study the subjective meanings and interpretations of social actors within their social and cultural context. Thus, our mode of reasoning is holistic and inductive, which favors the use of a qualitative approach. In this sense, Anadón & Guillemette (2006) specify that based on the epistemological foundations of qualitative research, it values inductive exploration and develops a holistic knowledge of reality. From this perspective, the knowledge production process takes on an inductive character because knowledge is produced from data. This method involves a comprehensive understanding of the data without having any prior theoretical preconception. Emerging themes are identified through inductive and iterative data analysis.

Our objective is to collect opinions and perceptions on the issue of our research from different SME stakeholders in the Souss Massa region.

To collect data relating to our subject of study, we carried out individual semi-structured interviews with managers of SMEs in the Souss Massa region with the aim of knowing to what extent the use of social media has an impact on the reputation of SMEs. These interviews lasted an average of 45 minutes and took place on the company premises. Respondents provided us, through a number of open-ended questions, with answers about the social media that are used by their companies, the level of influence of these media on the reputation of their organizations, and their perception of importance of adopting an effective media or digital communication policy on the reputation of their companies.

Regarding the composition of the sample, it is the managers of SMEs in the Souss Massa region who constitute the population concerned by our survey. Romelaer (2000) and Blanchot (2006) recommend carrying out interviews until a satisfactory degree of semantic saturation is obtained. As a result, we carried out 22 interviews with the managers of the SMEs that we were able to interview.

Thus, the choice of content analysis as a tool for processing the data collected was chosen in order to better analyze the information collected from SME managers in the Souss Massa region via the interview guide.

3. Presentation and discussion of results

In this part, we approach the last stage of our study, which consists of the presentation of the results obtained during the empirical study. We then discuss these results in order to achieve a more detailed analysis.

3.1. Result of the qualitative study

This part addresses the results obtained during the empirical research carried out using an interview guide comprising three axes of study. The first focuses on the use of social media by SMEs in the Souss Massa region, the second addresses the impact of interactions with social media on the reputation of SMEs, and the third examines the influence of a policy effective media on the reputation of SMEs.

3.1.1. Theme 1: The use of SMEs in the Souss Massa region on social media

Our interviewees say that their companies often use social media to communicate with their customers and prospects. One of the managers interviewed said that the rate of use has increased remarkably in recent years - it has become necessary to constantly communicate with customers through social media.

According to the statements of those interviewed, the social media used by the companies studied are mainly as follows:

- Social networks (Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, LinkedIn, Youtube)
- Emailing;
- Websites;
- Blogs.

The managers interviewed indicated that their company's presence on social media has an immediate and direct impact on their performance, results and general functioning.

3.1.2. Theme 2: The reputation of SMEs in light of their interactions on social media

The responses of the interviewees concerning the management of their online reputation, for some companies this task is carried out by a communications manager or a community

manager, for others this task is delegated to a communications agency. Their mission is to manage the company's various pages on social networks and to ensure its image and reputation online.

The entire population surveyed indicates that it is important to have procedures in place to manage negative comments on social media by regularly monitoring different social media to detect negative comments. One interviewee says this is done by using monitoring tools to track mentions of the company on social media and be alerted to negative comments in real time.

All the people we interviewed consider that their company's presence on social media has a significant impact on its reputation. It is important for them to effectively manage their social media presence, regularly monitor comments and ratings, and respond promptly to negative comments in order to protect their reputation and maintain a positive image among customers and prospects.

The SME managers we interviewed are divided between those who have already faced an online reputation crisis and those who have never had to face this problem. For those who have already encountered this type of problem, they have taken the necessary measures depending on the severity of the situation. Among the responses of those interviewed:

“The issue has impacted our reputation, leading us to work with relevant stakeholders to resolve the issue. This involved contacting unhappy customers, working with the communications manager to get a balanced version of the story, and even cooperating with the relevant authorities.”

“When we identified an online reputation crisis, we responded quickly by explaining the situation and offering solutions and alternatives. Of course, we apologized. We have avoided deleting negative comments, as this can make the situation worse.”

3.1.3. Theme 3: the contribution of an effective media policy to the reputation of SMEs

The interviewees' responses demonstrate that some of the companies studied do not have a clear social media policy, while others have a clearly defined social media policy. However, some officials described their policy by mentioning that:

- They view social media as an important communication channel to reach their customers, as well as provide excellent customer service.

- They make sure to use each platform in a way that suits their target audience and message.
- They have a dedicated team to manage their social media accounts.
- They have a strict content policy in place to ensure their messages are respectful, accurate and consistent with their ethics and values.
- They have security measures in place to protect their accounts and customer information.
- They use social media to monitor their audience's opinions and follow market trends. They use customer feedback to improve their products and services and maintain a relationship of trust with them.

In short, they have a clear and thoughtful social media policy that aims to maximize the benefits of social media while minimizing the risks.

The managers interviewed unanimously agreed that their social media policies are effective in improving the reputation of their companies. For them, social media has become an important way for businesses to connect with their customers and target audiences, and it is important to develop a strong and consistent presence on its platforms. For one manager, a simple presence on social media is not enough to improve a company's reputation. It is essential to have a clear and well-defined strategy for their social media presence, which takes into account their target audience, their business objectives and how they can use these platforms to achieve their goals.

According to all respondents from our target audience, a company's presence and monitoring on social media are essential to maintaining a good reputation. According to them, social media offers an opportunity to interact with customers, answer their questions and promote the company's brand image. Additionally, they also help monitor and manage the company's online reputation by quickly responding to negative comments or customer complaints. Ultimately, an active and regular presence on social media can help build credibility and trust with customers and business partners.

Based on our interviewees' responses, here are the strategies they use to improve their businesses' reputation on social media

- Creating professional profiles on social media related to their activity and maintaining an active presence on these platforms

- Regularly sharing quality, engaging content that piques user interest and reflects company values and identity
- Encouraging satisfied customers to leave positive reviews on social media and responding proactively and professionally to negative reviews
- Using social media to communicate company events and special offers and to quickly respond to customer questions
- Collaborating with influencers and bloggers to expand their audience and build credibility on social media
- Using monitoring tools to track mentions of their business on social media and quickly respond to customer questions and concerns.

Managers surveyed indicate that their companies plan to use social media to improve their reputation in the future by establishing a consistent presence across platforms, creating quality content, using social marketing techniques to increase reach and engagement, regularly monitoring comments and building partnerships with influential organizations and individuals. According to our interviewees, these steps should allow companies to create a strong and positive presence on social media, improve their reputation and strengthen their relationships with their target customers.

3.2. Discussion of results

We made three proposals. In this part, we will validate or refute them based on the results obtained during the empirical research.

Proposition 1: SMEs in the Souss Massa region use social media to be able to control and manage their reputation.

The interviews we conducted show that the companies surveyed use social media extensively to communicate with their customers and prospects, with a significant increase in its use in recent years. The most used platforms are social networks (Facebook, Instagram, Tiktok, LinkedIn, Youtube), emailing, websites and blogs. Thus, the people interviewed affirm that the presence of their company on social media has a direct impact on their performance, their results and their general functioning.

Therefore, we can affirm that our, proposition is validated.

Proposition 2: the reputation of SMEs is not affected by their interactions on social media.

According to our interview results, online reputation management is considered an important task for businesses. Managers surveyed said their companies often delegate this task to a communications manager, community manager, or communications agency, whose job is to manage the company's social media pages and monitor negative feedback in real-time. Thus, all those interviewed recognize that the online presence of their companies has a significant impact on their reputation and that effective management of their presence on social media is essential to maintain a positive image with customers and prospects. Some of the managers interviewed said their companies had previously experienced online reputation crises and had taken steps to resolve the problem. This included communicating with relevant stakeholders, finding a balanced version of the story with the communications manager, and even cooperating with the relevant authorities. Thus, in the event of a crisis, they affirmed that it is important to react quickly, explain the situation, offer solutions, and apologize if necessary while avoiding deleting negative comments that could make the situation worse.

To this extent, we can see that our second proposition is invalidated.

Proposition 3: the adoption of an effective policy on various social media strongly contributes to improving the reputation of SMEs.

Based on the results of the study, it appears that some companies do not have a clear social media policy, while others have a well-defined policy. Businesses that have a clear policy view social media as an important communication channel to reach their customers and have security measures in place to protect their accounts and customer information. They use social media to monitor public opinions and market trends, improve their products and services, and maintain a trusting relationship with their customers. The managers interviewed were all united in the fact that their social media policies are effective in improving the reputation of their companies. Social media presence and monitoring are considered essential for maintaining a good reputation and building credibility and trust with customers and business partners. Strategies used to improve their businesses' reputation on social media include creating professional profiles, sharing quality content, encouraging positive comments and responding to negative comments, communicating about events and special offers, working with influencers, and using monitoring tools to track company mentions. Businesses plan to

use social media in the future to establish a consistent presence, create quality content, regularly monitor comments, and partner with organizations and influencers to improve their reputation and strengthen relationships with their target customers.

We can therefore affirm that this proposition is validated.

Conclusion

This article aims to study the impact of social media on the reputation and e-reputation of SMEs. To do this, we mobilized, according to an interpretivist methodological approach, a set of theoretical concepts in order to describe what exists and to have a preliminary perception of the concepts studied. Indeed, we have formulated three proposals to put them to the test, namely: SMEs in the Souss Massa region use social media to be able to control and manage their reputation; the reputation of SMEs is not affected by their interactions on social media; the adoption of an effective policy on the various social media strongly contributes to improving the reputation of SMEs.

Subsequently, our qualitative study was carried out through semi-structured interviews with 22 managers of SMEs in the Souss Massa region, with a view to identifying effective measures and approaches that make it possible to know to what extent the use of social media improves the reputation of SMEs in the Souss Massa region. The analysis of the results of this study allowed us to answer the research question.

Ultimately, and in response to the stated problem, we can conclude that social media plays a major role in improving the reputation of SMEs in the Souss Massa region. Through effective use of social media, SMEs can increase their visibility, reach a wider audience, and interact with customers in a more direct and personalized way. SMEs thus gain trust and credibility, which helps improve their reputation. However, success on social media depends on many factors such as content quality, frequency of posts, marketing strategy, and engagement with internet users. SMEs must therefore adopt a strategic approach to make the most of social media and improve their reputation.

However, it is appropriate to put the results of this research into perspective in relation to the choices of investigations which can lead to the carrying out of a confirmatory quantitative study. The goal is to empirically test the reliability of the identified measurement elements in order to refine the conceptual model.

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